

The use of a laboratory workshop can also improve the students' understanding and performance of the experimental procedures. The findings of this study can be useful for instructors who aim to enhance the laboratory experience for their students and improve their learning outcomes. The use of a laboratory workshop was found to be highly effective in teaching elemental chemistry to first-year university students. The structured approach provided by the workshop allowed the students to work at their own pace and provided them with a clear understanding of the subject matter. The documentation required in the workshop also allowed the students to develop their skills in scientific writing and analysis. Based on these results, it is recommended that laboratory workshops be used in the teaching of elemental chemistry to first-year university students.

References

1. Farkas, G. (2014). The effectiveness of using laboratory workshops in chemistry education. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 91(6), 827-832.
2. Gormally, C., Brickman, P., Hallar, B., & Armstrong, N. (2009). Effects of a laboratory workshop on students' understanding of chemical concepts. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 86(11), 1316-1320.
3. Smith, M. K., Wood, W. B., & Knight, J. K. (2008). The benefits of using a laboratory workshop in a high school science class. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 45(6), 678-694.
4. Trundle, K. C., & Bell, R. L. (2020). The use of science notebooks in elementary classrooms. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 19(3), 266-277.
5. Pak M.S., Orlova I.A., Nekrasova G.V. Master's thesis in chemical education: A scientific and practical manual. - Publishing house of Russian State Pedagogical University named after A.I. Gertsen, 2008.
6. Zhanalieva R. N., Ungarbaeva A. S. Methodology of Chemical Experiment in Higher School. Textbook, - Shymkent: 2020-168 p.

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING CHEMISTRY BASED ON A CONNECTION WITH THE NATURAL SCIENCES

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Annotation. В статье рассматривается важность установления междисциплинарных связей с физикой при преподавании химии и ее роль в использовании химии как средства повышения интереса к обучению.

Keywords: Chemistry, Physics, interdisciplinary communication, subject integration

The state educational standard sets the task of quality training on the basis of active approaches to the education system. The student must take an active part in the educational process, have self-learning skills, and be able to navigate the information flow. The basis of educational activity is motives, needs and cognitive interest.

Currently, the integration of natural and technical knowledge is the basis of the current level of development of Science and technology. Cognitive interest in the study of non-core subjects, as a rule, is low in students. This problem can be solved taking into account the peculiarities of the educational and cognitive activity of students. To do this, it is necessary:

- Identification and development of conditions for the implementation of the potential opportunities of the educational process through interdisciplinary integration and the need for integration of subject teachers;

- Comprehensive development of students in the educational process, despite the insufficient integration of disciplines of the natural and mathematical cycle;

3. conducting integrated chemistry classes with Physics and mathematics, as well as interdisciplinary activities that contribute to increasing the level of motivation to study chemistry in students with a good level of training in the field of physics and mathematics.

Therefore, it is relevant to develop a methodology for conducting integrated classes in chemistry, which contributes to increasing the level of cognitive interest of students in the study of chemistry. Because if integration with physics and mathematics is carried out in the process of teaching chemistry, the level of cognitive interest of students in the study of chemistry increases.

Interdisciplinary integration is characterized by the following structure:

- by composition;
- in the direction of action;
- by the way the guide elements interact.

Interdisciplinary integrations in composition indicate what is used, changing from other academic disciplines when studying a particular topic. Interdisciplinary connections in the direction:

1) one, two or more academic disciplines, whether they are a source of interdisciplinary information for a specific subject of study under consideration, studied on a broad interdisciplinary basis.

2) interdisciplinary information is used only when studying the educational topic (direct links) of the basic academic discipline, or this topic is a "supplier" of formation instances for other topics, other disciplines of the curriculum (reverse or recovery links).

Time factor shows:

- what knowledge did students receive from other subjects, and what material still needs to be studied in the future (chronological links);
- in the process of implementing interdisciplinary connections, which topic is leading in terms of research deadlines, and which is not (chronological synchronous connections).
- how long does the interaction of topics last in the process of implementing interdisciplinary connections.

The above classification of interdisciplinary connections includes course connections (for example, connections between physics, mathematics, chemistry — a course of physics; connections between inorganic and organic chemistry — a course of chemistry), as well as internal connections between the topics of a particular academic discipline, for example, physics, Organic Chemistry. In intra- and intra-subject connections of chronological types, continuity and perspective types of connections prevail, while synchronous connections are sharply limited, and in subject connections there is no synchronous expression at all.

There are many things necessary to improve the educational process around the current question, to name a few of them: it is important to strengthen consistency in the content of the educational material of natural science disciplines; in methods and methods of teaching-activation of problematic, cognitive activity; in organizational forms — cooperation of teachers of various disciplines.

Analysis of students' abilities to study physics and Mathematics [1] it can be concluded that students of the physics and mathematics class are characterized by a combination of mathematical and natural-scientific directions of educational and cognitive processes [2]. The analysis below shows that students of physics and mathematics classes have the necessary abilities to study chemistry: analytical thinking, dynamics of thought processes, spatial thinking, and a tendency to abstraction. The chemistry course is able to form such students an understanding of the commonality of objects studied by physics and chemistry, the relationship between physical and chemical processes, physical research methods used in chemistry (methods of spectral and X-ray structural analysis, electron microscopy, etc.).

Chemistry and physics have a common subject area - the atomic and molecular levels of matter. Both Sciences use quantum mechanics and the same methods of analysis. When the elements of the general subject area of chemistry and physics are studied, it will be appropriate to establish a connection in teaching. It is also important to strengthen the mathematical apparatus of chemistry as an exact science [3].

Abilities in mathematical and Natural Science areas:

Mathematical direction:

Reception-Analytical;

Thinking-abstract-theoretical thinking; ease and breadth of generalization, depth of analysis; a wide range of thought processes; mathematical logic and reason; spatial thinking;

Memory -verbal-semantic, generalized, mathematical;

Fantasize-creative, spatial.

Natural Science direction:

Reception-Analytical

Thinking-theoretical thinking; combination of logical and figurative components; spatial thinking; modeling ability;

Memory -verbal-semantic, figurative;

Fantasizing - Creative.

Proceeding to the selection of the material with which the integration will be carried out, the following principles can be distinguished:

1.the chemical-physical content of the curriculum should be interrelated.

2.The Facts reported to the students must be correct: to the same extent in both subjects. Currently, the basic elements of Analytical Chemistry, Physical and physico-chemical methods of substance analysis are also included in the chemistry base of the school course: IR spectroscopy, X-ray analysis, NMR spectroscopy, mass spectrometry.

3.chemical-physical and mathematical teaching material should be accessible to students: correspond to the age of students and the level of theoretical training.

4. chemical-physical educational material should be a way to clarify and generalize the Natural Sciences. According to the definition of D. P. Ermygin: "interdisciplinary connections can be considered as a didactic system that reflects the relations objectively existing in school courses, ensuring the implementation of the goal of the directed process of teaching students through the coordinated interaction of its educational components." [4]

The use of interdisciplinary connections requires knowledge from the maintenance of curricula in other disciplines, the implementation of interdisciplinary connections in educational practice presupposes the difficulties of teachers of the Natural Science cycle. Analysis of the content of curricula in physics and chemistry in senior grades [5, 6] made it possible to determine the amount of information that can be used in the school course to implement interdisciplinary integration

In conclusion, the importance of conducting classes related to the subject of physics of chemistry is high, which contributes to increasing the level of cognitive interest in the study of chemistry. Educational goals the integration of two related disciplines is the only reason for students to perceive the educational material more thoroughly.

Literature:

1. Arshansky E. Ya. specifics of teaching chemistry in physical and mathematical classes // chemistry in school.— 2002. - No. 6. - pp. 23-29.

2. Arshansky E. Ya. study of chemistry in specialized classes. "I don't know," he said.- M.: Centrhimpress, 2004. -128 P.

3. Afanasekova, I. V. international integration as part of increasing interest in studying chemistry in physical and mathematical schools / I. V. Afanasekova, A. A. Baitulesova. // Young scientist. — 2022. — № 24 (419). — Pp. 335-339.

4. Coordination and methods of ensuring the inter-border connection in the course of chemistry. Methodical recommendations / Sost. Erygin D. P. and Dyakova M. B.-M., 1988. – 92p.

5. The type of educational program for the educational program "Physics" for 10-11 classes of industrial and mathematical direction of the area of public secondary education on expanded education- Astana: NAO im. I. Altynsarina, 2013. - 28 p.

6. The type of educational program for the educational program "Chemistry" for 10-11 classes of industrial and mathematical direction of the area of public secondary education on expanded education- Astana: NAO im. I. Altynsarina, 2013. - 29 p.

THE FEATURE OF USING NEW INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN CHEMISTRY LESSONS

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